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NAMES OF DISEASES AND THEIR USE IN CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the analysis of the names of diseases used in the process of communication between a doctor and a patient. Particular attention is paid to the criteria for the availability of special information for those who act as patients. The author conducts typological studies of the characteristic features of the names of diseases and makes an attempt to classify them, taking into account the possible stylistic range of these nominations.

Keywords: name, disease, classification, signs, doctor's speech

In clinical terminology, "sick" is "one who is in pain." The European word "patient" (from the Latin form *pati* - "I endure", endure) has a different semantic connotation. The patient is "one who endures", "suffers". The patient (patient) first of all tries to find out his diagnosis from the doctor. Understanding medical terms can be difficult for a non-specialist, despite the fact that the patient may be a highly educated person and have free access to existing vocabulary and reference literature and Internet resources. Every person is susceptible to illness. Disease (synonym - *morbis*) from the Latin *morbis* is a state of the body, expressed in the restriction or disruption of its normal and habitual life, in some cases, affecting its performance, socially useful activity and even life expectancy.

The disease affects the ability of a person to adapt to changing conditions of the external and internal environment, while causing the activation of his protective reactions. "Disease" in the broadest sense of the word means any, obvious or hidden, instantaneous or long-term, deviation from the normal state, which will certainly affect the appearance of a person, the characteristics of his behavior (posture, mood, reaction), caused by changes in the functions of an organ, group organs or the body as a whole. In essence, a disease is a response of some part of the body or its systems to damage, infection or other factors of influence. The causes of diseases are diverse and numerous,

which makes it possible to classify them according to various typological characteristics. During life, a person may have 1) congenital diseases; 2) infectious diseases; 3) diseases of metabolic disorders; 4) deficiency diseases; 5) tumor diseases; 6) diseases caused by physical or chemical influences, poisons and intoxication; 7) degenerative diseases; 8) allergic diseases. Depending on the age, gender, professional affiliation, diseases of children, women, men, occupational diseases, diseases of the elderly are distinguished.

The classification of diseases occurs according to which organs or systems of the body they affect: diseases of the digestive system, diseases of the cardiovascular system, nervous diseases, internal diseases, respiratory diseases, eye diseases, and many others. Congenital refers to diseases (diseases) inherent in a person from birth (for example, malformations and intrauterine infections). Acquired diseases include diseases resulting from everyday and professional activities of a person: injuries, bruises, cuts, infections, damage to various organs, malnutrition, physical overload, etc. The causes of diseases are varied, but they all come down to strictly defined groups: mechanical, physical, chemical, biological, psychogenic.

Any of these factors causes a state of illness if it is inadequate for the body. Inadequacy can be quantitative, qualitative, temporary and depending on the individual properties of the human body. In different people, the disease proceeds in different ways, which is influenced by the physical capabilities of the body, the timely provision of quality medical care and subsequent care for the patient. The following periods of the disease should be distinguished:

1) Latent, or latent (for infectious diseases - incubation), - the period between the onset of the pathogenic effect and the appearance of the first symptoms of the disease. It can last from a few seconds (for example, when poisoning with strong poisons) to tens of years (for example, with leprosy).

2) Prodromal period - the period of the appearance of the first signs of the disease, which may be of an indefinite non-specific nature (fever, weakness, general malaise) or in some cases be typical for this disease (for example, characteristic spots with measles or chickenpox).

3) The period of full development of the disease, the duration of which varies from several days to tens of years (tuberculosis, syphilis, leprosy).

4) The period of completion of the disease (quick or gradual recovery, full or partial return to the usual way of life, loss of ability to work, acquisition of disability). According to the nature of the course of the disease, acute diseases and chronic diseases are distinguished. According to the level at which specific pathological changes are detected in the body, molecular diseases, chromosomal diseases, cellular diseases, tissue diseases, organ diseases, diseases of the whole organism are distinguished.

In official papers, medical certificates and documents, as well as in communication with colleagues (conciliums), the doctor must use the terms of the international nomenclature, terms based on Greek-Latin names (mastitis - breast, hepatitis - jaundice, diarrhea - diarrhea, alopecia - baldness, pediculosis - lice, carcinoma - cancer).

But when communicating verbally with the patient, the doctor is obliged to explain the nature of his disease and the possible consequences of the disease, and this should be done in the Russian literary language, given that the specialist is an interested person who is far from the medical profession. Examples: "You have amnesia, that is, loss of memory, especially for recent important events." "Your child's diagnosis is enuresis.

This is bedwetting, a disease that affects many children." "X-ray examinations showed that you have pneumonia - this is inflammation of the lungs. The disease developed against the background of chronic bronchitis. "Your son has epilepsy, a severe and, unfortunately, one of the most common chronic neurological diseases. The cause of epilepsy was a cyst in the brain. Seizures may occur during seizures. The speech of the patient when presenting complaints is far from normative.

Popular names of diseases (colloquial - epilepsy, varicose veins, coronary heart disease, insanity, burr, nasality, gonorrhoea, bazedka, colloquial - bumps on the legs, pemphigus, cleft lip, cleft palate, goosebumps, night blindness, dialectal - kondrashka, twist, fever, dormouse, freckles, fever), as well as socially marked names of diseases (slang - caisson, squirrel, venus; slang - shiz, depression, shaking, breaking, dryness) is quite common in the speech of sick people who experience acute pain and lose control over your well-being. There are possible narrow professional names of diseases that are familiar only to representatives of certain professions - miners, loaders, hairdressers, drivers.

Many popular names of diseases have become normative and entered the dictionaries of medical terms (thrush, erysipelas, scabies, mumps, dropsy, chest, urticaria, jaundice). Some names of diseases have retained a transparent etymology (clubfoot, flat feet, farsightedness, myopia, strabismus, baldness, deafness) and are quite understandable to native Russian speakers. If the patient does not understand the meaning of the term, the doctor may resort to a detailed and accessible explanation of the disease.

Great difficulties arise when the names of the doctors who first described them, the so-called eponyms, are found in the names of diseases: Bechterov's disease, Coppock's disease, Reiter's disease, Huntington's disease, Werlhof's disease, Alzheimer's disease. In communication with the patient, the use of terms performs not only a nominative, but also a communicative function.

The speech act of a specialist takes place in a certain communicative environment and is performed in the interests of the addressee. For example: "The Parkinson's disease that you suffer from is the result of damage to the nervous system. The disease is characterized by a decrease in general motor activity and slowness of movements, trembling of the limbs, and an increase in muscle tone.

"Your exact diagnosis is onkylosing spondylitis, or Strümpell-Bechterew-Marie disease, remember that this is a chronic systemic disease of the joints and ligaments.

The disease is caused by various reasons. For its early diagnosis, we will perform x-rays in special projections and laboratory tests, including genetic ones." Thus, when communicating between a doctor and a patient, it is necessary to take into account a certain level of development of medical knowledge in the modern cultural and speech situation.

In everyday communication of specialists with patients, the concept of the "circle of diseases" is taken into account. This circle is associated not only with detailed scientific medical terminology, but also with the real environment in which the patient is located. When meeting with a doctor, he has to give the most accurate and complete explanation of the characteristic signs of his disease to the best of his ability and ability. The experience of classifying diseases in the Russian-speaking environment has a certain tradition. It is possible to classify the names of diseases, in which the nominations are combined, first of all, according to the subject sign (lexemes denoting diseases).

Firstly, a logical criterion is proposed (general and special names of diseases are studied), and, secondly, a linguistic approach is put forward: the linguistic material is considered from the point of view of syntactic constructions describing the state of the disease, structural characteristics are studied in the distinguished synonymic rows and various semantic models of word formation. In a broad medical and anthropological vein - with the involvement of traditional medicine - a historical and cultural approach to the problems of studying the language of medicine is being formed.

At the same time, cultural-anthropological, ethnological grounds are visible in the names of diseases. The idea of material analysis proposed in this paper is based on real medical practice, based on an integrative approach, in which an alloy of cultural, anthropological and medical components is found and organically coexists. The category that shapes this situation is undoubtedly medical experience.

Actually, the defining criterion for the classification of diseases in this article is the specificity of medical experience in the culture of the Russian nation, which, on the one hand, reflects a certain quality of medical knowledge, and on the other hand, implicitly preserves some cultural attitudes that manifest themselves in the linguistic consciousness through the prism of the medical vocabulary of the living language.

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